

The Role of the Village Head in Efforts to Increase Community Participation in Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District, North Gorontalo Regency

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Role of Village Head, Community Participation, Sea Pearl Village

Received : 05, September

Revised : 15, September

Accepted: 22, October

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to obtain an overview of the role of the village head in efforts to increase community participation in Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District, North Gorontalo Regency. This research is qualitative research with descriptive methods. The location of this research is in Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District, North Gorontalo Regency. The research to be carried out uses 2 (two) types of data sources, namely: Primary Data and Secondary Data. Data collection techniques used in this study are: observation, interviews, and document review. Data Analysis techniques used are data reduction, data presentation, and conclusions. The results showed that the role of the Village Head in efforts to increase community participation in Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District, North Gorontalo Regency has not been optimal, because the implementation of the development program still has problems in the field that should be evaluated.

INTRODUCTION

The role of the Village Head greatly determines the development of the village. To mobilize the community to participate in development, it is necessary to have a driving force / element to move and direct the community's ability to realize the ideals of development in this relationship, so the village head as the village head plays a decisive role. As the highest leader and person in charge of the implementation of governance and development, the government must be able to coordinate as units in government in order to use their functions well and make a real contribution to the development process.

In its implementation, village development always pays attention to the principles of development that all development efforts and activities must provide the greatest benefit for humanity, for improving the welfare of the people and for the personal development of the community. For this reason, the government must know that the implementation of increasing community participation must be integrated and cooperate with the community

The people of mutiara laut village really need infrastructure and facilities to make it easier for their people to carry out their daily activities and produce agricultural products. Mutiara Laut Village has three hamlets with a population of 488 people including 269 men and 219 women with 142 families including 197 farmers, 70 fishermen and 2 employees working in the office.

The implementation of village government programs that focus on improving the development of the villages where they live, so that they have more responsibility to maintain and maintain or even improve the quality of village development in a better direction, but there are still Village Programs that cannot be completed such as road infrastructure in 2018 at the beginning of the construction of roads as a means of transportation connecting one village to another Over time in 2022 the road was demolished and repaired with the road widening infrastructure development program, but the construction of road infrastructure as an effort to improve the welfare of the village community has not been completed until now, the road is increasingly damaged due to waterlogging and landslides. The existence of these problems makes the road can no longer be passed by vehicles, because damaged and supervising roads can interfere with the community in issuing agricultural products so that they only use sea transportation which is very expensive because there has been no road repair as the main means of transportation.

Based on the results of the researcher's initial observations, that there is still a lack of optimal road infrastructure development planning such as during the infrastructure development planning deliberation or Musrenbang was still little attended by community leaders, but most of those present were from village officials and only a small part of community leaders. So that information on development plans caused by lack of participation of rural communities is not generally known by the community. And the development policy-making process is known only to a small part of the public.

In addition, the implementation of development has not run optimally due to the lack of participation of the village community there are several problems, such as the implementation of development in the village is not in

accordance with what was proposed during village deliberations, namely the road infrastructure development plan which until now has not been implemented until now resulting in unable to release agricultural products due to damaged road infrastructure cannot be passed by vehicles,

In addition, there is still a lack of role of village heads in increasing village community participation such as lack of community participation in musrenbang, many MSMEs cannot run and infrastructure development programs are hampered because people who come to participate in musrenbang which includes development programs and village business development are only a few so that it can hamper development planning to increase village community participation in all programs.

The role of the village head in the implementation of development programs such as the implementation of development programs in the field of village business units to increase community participation in Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District. Therefore, the success of development needs to increase the participation of the village community in an area is determined by the role of the village head and the government. Starting point in the implementation of increasing village community participation, especially in Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District, North Gorontalo Regency.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Public Administration

According to Simon in Rahman (2017; 6) administration as a group activity that collaborates to complete tasks with Dwight Waldo in Syafri (2015: 10) administration as "*Cooperative rational action*" (rational cooperation effort) is a group of people cooperation activities carried out efficiently to achieve the desired goals. Woodrow Wilson in Syafri (2015: 21) stated that public administration is the business or practice of government affairs because the purpose of government is to carry out public work efficiently and as far as possible to suit the tastes / desires of the people.

Leadership

Leadership is part of management functions that occupy strategic positions in the system and hierarchy of work and responsibility in an organization Nasharuddin (2014: 126). According to Hasibuan (2015: 13) argues that leadership is someone who uses his authority and leadership to direct others and is responsible for the work of that person in achieving a goal. Danang Sunyoto (2015: 34), argues that leadership is an organization, the nature and attitude of a leader's leadership to influence others is very decisive in achieving organizational goals. From the various understandings and opinions of the experts above, it can be concluded that leadership is the ability of a leader to influence and move others to work together in achieving a goal in an organization.

The Role of the Village Head

A role is an action carried out by someone where the action can provide something that society expects (Lepa et al., 2019: 32). Sociologically, role is a form of attitude or movement carried out in society in order to carry out its position where in that position there are rights and obligations that have been arranged to be carried out as stakeholders of a certain position. According to Widjajah (2015: 27) the village head is the highest ruler in the village and as a formal and informal leader, a leader who is at all times in the midst of the people he leads.

In organizing village government, the Village Head together with the Village Consultative Body (BPD) are assisted by village officials. For the smooth implementation of government effectively and successfully in accordance with the objectives of village development, it requires ability, intelligence, skills in addition to other requirements administratively.

The village head has the obligation to provide reports on the implementation of village government to the regent/mayor, provide accountability information reports, and inform reports on the implementation of village government to the community. Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the village head is a leader in the village government who is strategically positioned and has broad responsibilities.

Village Government

Village government according to Law No. 6 of 2014 article 25 explains that village government is the village head or what is called by other names and who is assisted by devices or called by other names. Village government is the government's efforts to improve the standard of living of the community. Village government according to Saparin (2019: 19) in his book, said that "Government in a broad sense is all affairs carried out by the state in carrying out the welfare of its people and the interests of the state itself, if it is not interpreted as a government that only runs the executive, but also includes other duties including legislative and judicial. Village government according to Surasih (201:6:23) is a process in which the efforts of the village community concerned are combined with village government administration.

Participation

According to Made Pidarta in Siti Irene Astuti D. (2019: 31-32), participation is the involvement of a person or several people in an activity. Involvement can be in the form of mental and emotional and physical involvement in using all the abilities they have (initiative) in all activities carried out and supporting the achievement of goals and responsibilities for all involvement.

Community participation according to Isbandi (2013: 27) is community participation in the process of identifying problems and potentials that exist in the community, selection and decision making on alternative solutions to deal with problems, implementing efforts to overcome problems, and community involvement in the process of evaluating changes that occur.

In addition to the above opinions, Mulyadi (2015: 13) said that Community Participation is community participation in the decision-making process and running a program, where the community also benefits from the program policy. In addition, in conducting a community evaluation, of course, they are also involved in order to improve community welfare

Figure 1. The Role of the Head of Desa

METODOLOGY

This research is qualitative research with descriptive methods. According to Sugiono (2015: 206), the research conducted is descriptive, namely to find out or describe the reality of the events studied regarding the role of the village head in efforts to increase community participation in Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District, North Gorontalo Regency. The location of this research is in Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District, North Gorontalo Regency. The research to be carried out uses 2 (two) types of data sources, namely: Primary Data The primary data includes; 1 village head, 1 village secretary, 1 government officer, 1 development person, 1 BPD person, 2 community members with a total number of 7 informants. and secondary data. Data collection techniques used in this study are: observation, interviews, and document review. Data Analysis techniques used are data reduction, data presentation, and conclusions.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Planning

Planning is said to be a series of decisions made as guidelines that become a benchmark in the implementation of activities to achieve a goal with available resources. Based on an interview with the Key Informant of the Village Head (DR) he stated:

"The background of village development planning includes setting program priorities and village needs to be funded. Then it was discussed in Musrenbangdes. So in terms of planning, it is clear that I as the village head and village officials play an active role, but what is an obstacle in planning formulation lies in the lack of people present in the musrenbang for road

infrastructure development planning and others where only a few people come so that development planning cannot be optimal" (interview, July 13, 2023).

Furthermore, emphasized by (TA) the village secretary he said that:

"The role of the village head in increasing community participation in planning is good, where before the implementation of the program, the village head carried out a development plan starting with a village musrenbang, what were the needs of the program and its implementation, but during deliberation, many people did not provide aspirations, input and suggestions so they only followed and agreed to the existing development program without participating in making the development planning design, all submitted to the head of DSA and the village government so that development is not in accordance with the wishes and expectations of the community" (interview, July 13, 2023).

Furthermore, conducting interviews (AB) of the community he explained that:

"The role of the village head in planning, in my opinion, has not been maximized because when musrenbang there was an agreement on the planned program, but the implementation was different and it was not implemented what had been agreed and had to see what the community needs" (interview, July 15, 2023).

Furthermore, conducting an interview with BPD (DK) he explained that:

"The role of the village head in increasing community participation in development planning is good, where I always hold musrenbang meetings before implementation, I am also present at the meeting, but it cannot be denied that only a few people come and that will cause problems in the future, no matter how the community should actively participate in the planning process, and the implementation of development programs due to the fact that the lack of community involvement of the program is experienced problems even programs cannot be optimized and completed" (interview, July 17, 2023).

Furthermore, conducting an interview with (FY) kasie government he explained that:

"In every development carried out in this village, there are always instructions from the village government, especially the village head. to always deliberate on program planning, especially infrastructure development programs to increase community income with BPD and other community leaders, from which deliberation is held for the implementation of directed development, so as to create development that is in accordance with mutual expectations So that the one who plays the most role here is the village chief. However, the lack of aspirational input and advice from the community in program planning deliberations can hinder future development" (interview, July 17, 2023).

From the informant's statement above, it shows that the village head has increased community participation in planning infrastructure development programs that have been running where before the implementation of planning was held with the beginning of deliberation with BPD and the community for the implementation of directed development but development program planning has not been optimal due to lack of aspirations, input and suggestions

from the community in deliberations And in the implementation of Musrenbang, there has been an agreement on the development program, but the implementation of the program is different, what should be a mutual agreement, if there is a change, it must be re-deliberated, that's where the problem arises that the development program does not meet the expectations of the village community.

Implementation

The implementation of development, in the role of the village head, increases community participation in the implementation of the development program of Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District, North Gorontalo Regency regarding, the process of determining the implementers of development activities. Through an interview conducted with the village head (DR) said that:

"For this stage of infrastructure development, in the implementation of the development program, in my opinion, it is good where before the implementation was held, planning deliberations were held to initiate development programs to increase the income of the village community, I as the village head always instructed in the implementation of development to involve the role of the village government as well as assisted by community participation, but in this village the obstacles during its implementation still exist People who are ignorant do not want to participate in development program activities to increase community income even though this development is also for the needs of the village community". (interview, July 13, 2023).

Furthermore, conducting an interview (RP) kasie development he explained that:

"Regarding the role of the village head in the implementation of development is very lacking, it can be seen that only a few people who participate in the development program should be demanded an extra role of the village head to increase public awareness to want to participate in this development program activity because in the future those who feel development are also the community itself so as the village head must be able to invite and cooperate with the community for the smooth running of the program development". (interview, July 13, 2023).

Furthermore, conducting an interview (DK) BPD he explained that:

"The role of the village head in the implementation of infrastructure development programs has not run optimally where the village head has not been able to embrace and invite the community to participate directly in every development program. It is seen that in the implementation of the program, there are less people who participate, where when invited to a meeting, only a few come after the implementation is just that, others are ignorant and do not want to know so that the implementation of this program has not been said to be optimal in terms of community participation, that is where the extra role of the village head is demanded to invite and embrace the community to want to participate in the activities of this development program" (interview, July 17, 2023).

Furthermore, conducting interviews (AP) the community he explained that:

"The role of the village head in the implementation of development programs has not been maximized, there is no cooperation between the government and the community, which results in a lack of understanding of development programs that are running to increase community income, which should involve the community directly in the implementation of the program, that's where the problem arises where the lack of cooperation with the community results in the community not participating in the implementation of development programs and only being The audience who should be directly involved so that a lot of work is not completed, it can be said that the implementation of the village infrastructure development program cannot be optimized". (interview, July 15, 2023)

From the informant's statement above, it shows that the role of the village head in increasing community participation in the implementation of infrastructure development programs has not been optimal, judging from the lack of community participation, therefore the extra role of the village head is demanded to increase public awareness to want to participate in development program activities and the lack of cooperation between the village government and the community That's where the problem arises where the community does not participate in the implementation of the program and only becomes a spectator who should be directly involved which results in the program not being completed and not optimal.

Evaluation

Development program evaluation is a series of activities carried out deliberately to see the success rate of infrastructure development programs to increase the income of rural communities in other words, development program evaluation is intended to see the achievement of the development program targets. The evaluation referred to in this study is the role of the village head in evaluating the development program of Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District, North Gorontalo Regency as well as interviews conducted by researchers with key informants or key informants, namely the Village Head (DR), he stated that:

"I always evaluate development programs to increase the income of existing communities where at the end of each program completion I always hold a final meeting to evaluate what shortcomings and problems occur in the program activities so that the next year there will not be a repeat of the same problems in development to increase the income of rural communities cannot be optimized" (interview, July 13, 2023).

Furthermore, conducting an interview (FY) with the government he explained that:

"The role of the village head in evaluating the development program is good and quite instrumental because every time the program is finished, a meeting is held to evaluate the program, what are the obstacles and problems so that in the future the same mistakes will not occur" (interview, July 17, 2023).

Furthermore, conducting an interview (TA) his secretary explained that:

"The role of the village head in evaluating the development implementation program is good, it's just that it needs to be optimized because every program ends up in a program evaluation meeting so that in the future there are no problems that should not only wait for the program to end but the program should run, the village head must continue to supervise and evaluate the program so that there are no mistakes" (interview, July 13, 2023).

Furthermore, conducting interviews (AB) of the community he explained that:

"In my opinion, the role of the village head in evaluating village activities is very lacking, where only at the end of the program sometimes it is not even evaluated, the village head and village government should always evaluate every program so that the problems that occur can be resolved immediately, for example, when community planning conveys aspirations for road construction programs, but when the implementation arrives there are problems, the role of the village head should immediately improve and evaluate them not picking up the program ended and then evaluated" (interview, July 15, 2023).

Based on the results of interviews with some of the informants above, it can be seen that the role of the village head in evaluating the program is very lacking, there should be an evaluation of every running program and must involve the community directly in the implementation of the program so that the community can also provide input and suggestions so that the input and suggestions of the community can have a positive impact on the smooth running of development programs to increase the income of the community.

In other words, the role of the village head in evaluating village development programs has been running but has not been optimized because during the implementation of the program there are problems in the field that should be evaluated and resolved immediately but in reality they are not. Evaluation is only carried out every time the program is completed which should not only wait for the program to be completed and then conduct an evaluation, but the evaluation is carried out every time the process of implementing the development program so that there are no mistakes and involving the community directly in the implementation of the program so that the community can also provide input and suggestions, the input and suggestions of the community can have a positive impact for the smooth running of the program Building.

DISCUSSION

According to Tjokroamidjojo in (Syafalevi, 2013: 28) planning in the broadest sense is a process of systematically preparing activities that will be carried out to achieve a certain goal. Planning can be used to control and evaluate the course of activities, because the nature of the plan is as a guideline for the implementation of activities. Based on the results of the research that the role of the village head in increasing community participation in planning infrastructure development programs has been running where before the implementation of planning was held with the beginning of deliberation with BPD and the community for the implementation of directed development but

development program planning has not been optimal due to the lack of aspirations, input and suggestions from the community in deliberations and in the implementation of musrenbang. There is an agreement on the development program, but the implementation of the program is different, what should be a mutual agreement, if there is a change, it must be re-deliberated, that's where the problem arises that the development program does not meet the expectations of the village community.

According to Abdullah (2014: 151) implementation is a process of a series of program follow-up activities or policies determined consisting of decision making, strategic or operational steps or policies become a reality in order to achieve the targets of the originally determined program. The village head certainly has a very big role in the implementation of village development which is a mandate given by the community to make the area much improved than before. Based on the results of the study, the role of the village head in increasing community participation in the implementation of infrastructure development programs has not been optimal, judging from the lack of community participation, therefore the extra role of the village head is demanded to increase public awareness to want to participate in development program activities and the lack of cooperation between the village government and the community. That's where the problem arises where the community does not participate in the implementation of the program and only becomes a spectator who should be directly involved which results in the program not being completed and not optimal.

Furthermore, Mohammad Ali (2014: 23) said that evaluation is an activity that is usually carried out to make an assessment of the feasibility of planning, implementation, and results of a program or policy. Based on the results of the study that the role of the village head in evaluating the village development program has been running but has not been optimized because during the implementation of the program there are problems in the field that should be evaluated and resolved immediately but in reality they are not. Evaluation is only carried out every time the program is completed which should not only wait for the program to be completed and then evaluate, but evaluation is carried out every time the process of implementing the development program so that there are no mistakes and involving the community directly in the implementation of the program so that the community can also provide input and suggestions, the input and suggestions of the community can have a positive impact on the smooth running of the development program.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The role of the village head in increasing community participation in planning infrastructure development programs has been running but has not been optimal due to the lack of people who come, lack of aspirations, input and suggestions from the community in deliberations. The role of the village head in increasing community participation in the implementation of infrastructure development programs has not been optimal seen from the lack of community

participation, as well as the role of the village head in evaluating village development programs has been running but has not been optimized because the evaluation is only carried out every program is completed which should not just wait for the program to be completed and then mel a However, the evaluation is carried out every time the process of implementing the development program so that errors do not occur. Therefore, the role of village heads in increasing community participation in planning infrastructure development programs needs to be optimized with various alternative approaches to the community. The village head must also be able to invite and embrace the community to participate in working together in the implementation of development programs, for this reason, the role of the village head is very important in the success of the implementation of development in the village, and the implementation of the program evaluation needs to be improved not only at the end of the new program, an evaluation meeting is held, but when the program is running, the village head must continue provide supervision and evaluate each development program.

FURTHER STUDY

Each research has limitations, as is the case with my research on the Role of Village Heads in Efforts to Increase Community Participation in Mutiara Laut Village, Tomilito District, North Gorontalo Regency which focuses on aspects of planning, implementation and evaluation as a benchmark in this study so that this research still has many limitations, therefore, to the next researcher to further add context and scope More complex research so that relevant research results are of higher quality.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The highest gratitude to Allah SWT, to your parents, to the Rector, Vice Rector, Dean, Head of Study Program, to all lecturers, all employees, and to all friends who always provide support, direction and motivation to researchers so that researchers can complete this research in a timely manner.

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